

8T – Primorial as a Wave Equation

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T, author will present a new variation of the primorial, which include a five-vector. Such a representation will be used to answer the question regarding the motion of particles on the surface of the manifold. That will be done via subscript on the lepton and the Boson.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equation (1) By (1.2A) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.4)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1.41)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.42)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation. We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matrix tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

Let us analyze the idea of a positional primorial, which is constructed to provide a solution to the question of position. To solve the issue of position the author will use a five- vector on the subscript. The three spatial coordinates, one temporal and the index of the manifold on the packet.

$$F_{R\#} = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V \rightarrow \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3)_\mu \right) + N_{V\mu}$$

Assuming the even sum has vanished into matter, which means it stands for the nuclei, from which the electron propagate, we than are required to insert the subscript to that term as well.

$$\left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3)_\mu \right) + N_{V\mu} \rightarrow \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + (3)_\mu \right) + N_{V\mu}$$

$$\mu = (\nabla^2, t_n, s_n)$$

The time is indexed as to represent the idea of unique arrow to each manifold. The additional subscript on the primorial allows us to expend the idea and include positional variables with temporal variables. Since the 8T was built upon an Euler Lagrange framework which yields an equation of motion that is invariant to changes of coordinate so does the primorial is invariant, and assumed relativistic. The invariance of the primorial is also due to the invariance of the prime ring. In no frame of reference does the primes change their order nor their innate values. Any observer clever enough will find that the primes are at the heart of the coupling magnitudes, does not vary if measured from that coordinate or another. That is because in all frames of reference arbitrary variations are vanishing onto matter, while primes are possessing a non-vanishing nature, which is a feature universal to all observers, i.e. all matter clusters of distinct amounts. We can go further and state a morphism similar to the term presented in the non-relativistic Schrodinger equation:

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t_n^2} N_V = \nabla^2 N_{V s_n} \quad (1.32)$$

Which means that instead of a wave propagation in space, we have net curvature ripple propagation in space. As the curvature ripple propagates over larger matrix tensor surface, the ripple gets weaker and weaker. That is somewhat a more modern version of the Coulomb law and the Newton law, which regard force to be inversely proportional to the square of the distance. Alternatively, if we consider that the Laplace operator already contain the unique manifold, $s_n \in \nabla^2$ than (1.32) takes the simpler form:

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t_n^2} N_V = \nabla^2 N_V \quad (1.33)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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